

STRUCTURE OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Highly competent and pedagogical skills, competitive, creative and creative, able to continuously develop their potential, along with research aimed at solving existing and future social problems in the field of education at the international level. Special attention is being paid to improving the training mechanisms of pedagogic personnel and clarifying the competence requirements. The best experiences and results of scientific research are the internationalization and modernization of the content of modern professional education, the formation of an innovative educational environment based on competences, the improvement of mechanisms for the creation of modern methodological support for the design of the creative educational process, and the guidance of teachers to the fields of professional activity. is reflected in pedagogical activities aimed at developing pedagogical skills.*

Keywords: *structure of professional abilities of higher education teacher, professional ability, organizational ability, gnostic ability, epistemological component, communicative component.*

Highly competent and pedagogical skills, competitive, creative and creative, able to continuously develop their potential, along with research aimed at solving existing and future social problems in the field of education at the international level. Special attention is being paid to improving the training mechanisms of pedagogic personnel and clarifying the competence requirements. The best experiences and results of scientific research are the internationalization and modernization of the content of modern professional education, the formation of an innovative educational environment based on competences, the improvement of mechanisms for the creation of modern methodological support for the design of the creative educational process, and the guidance of teachers to the fields of professional activity. is reflected in pedagogical activities aimed at developing pedagogical skills.

Personal-pedagogical values appear as socio-psychological education, and they reflect the goals, motives, ideals and other features of the teacher's personality. The set of these features forms its value orientation system. Axiological "I" as a direction of values includes not only cognitive (cognitive) components, but also an emotional-volitional component that plays an important role in the inner direction of a person includes parts.

It includes professional and collective values that serve as the basis for both the social-pedagogical and the individual-personal system of pedagogical values. if there are external objective components, the methods and methods of scientific-pedagogical activity will have an individual and subjective character. Their use depends on the ability of each teacher. Despite the fact that professional abilities are unevenly manifested in the work of a higher education specialist, they are usually considered as a complex combination, as well as a structure of personal characteristics related to a specific activity. Along with complex special abilities, necessary in pedagogical work Elementary general abilities such as observation, speech qualities, thinking, imagination also play a big role, if the specialist who acquires them quickly and correctly

recognizes a unique feature with their help. evaluates the important features of the pedagogical system, the science, the processes taking place in them, and the effectiveness of the management goals. Pedagogical skills are usually included in the organizational and gnostic skills discussed below, although these skills can exist separately from each other: communicating one's knowledge to others, even there are scientists who lack the ability to explain what they understand well. Pedagogical skills required for a professor giving a course to students and a scientist - the head of a laboratory are different. In the 60s, F.N.Gonobolin[1] gave the following personal characteristics, the composition of which, in his opinion, constitutes true pedagogical skills:

- ability to make educational material convenient;
- creativity in work;
- exerting pedagogical and voluntary influence on students;
- the ability to organize a student team;
- interest and love for children;
- the content and brightness of the speech, its imagery and persuasiveness;
- pedagogical tact;
- the ability to connect the subject with life;
- monitoring;
- pedagogical demand;

The personal characteristics of a teacher include: organization, work ability, curiosity, self-control, activity, persistence, concentration and distribution. Academic skills often include constructive, projective and organizational skills. Organizational skills may not have been part of the skills required for a single scientist in the 18th and 19th centuries. However, modern science cannot be realized without a team, a scientist must be an organizer, otherwise he cannot fully realize himself[2]. Also, special abilities arising from innate anatomical and physiological characteristics to the science teacher, that is, musical and artistic abilities for musicians and art historians, philological abilities for those related to literary creation, mathematical abilities for mathematicians and physicists. necessary. Now we will consider the main components of the professional skills of a university teacher.

1. Epistemological component. Epistemological skills express the teacher's sensitivity to the methods of obtaining information about the world, students, in general, the formation of moral, labor, and intellectual foundations of a person, rapid and creative mastering of scientific research methods. studying students in connection with the goals of personality formation. Gnostic skills enable students to gather information effectively about themselves and others, which control and allows to stimulate the formation of self-management. It caters to students' needs and capabilities, strengths and weaknesses.

A sign of highly developed gnostic abilities is rapid and creative assimilation of scientific methods of learning for students to make informed decisions about them, self-education, self-development and self-management. is the ingenuity of teaching scientific methods. An important component of the gnostic component is the knowledge and skills that are the basis of one's cognitive activity.

The gnostic component affects the formation of a worldview that is manifested in a system of stable relationships with the world, work, other people and oneself; about the activity of the vital position. General cultural knowledge, skills in art and literature, religion, law, politics and social life, environmental problems are also important. Having meaningful interests and hobbies also enriches the personality of a highly educated professional. Special knowledge - knowledge of science, pedagogy, psychology, teaching methodology. Knowledge of the subject is highly valued

by teachers and at a high level. Knowledge of psychology, pedagogy and methodology is the weakest link of higher education.

2. Constructive-projective component. Gnostic skills form the basis of the teacher's activity, but constructive and projective skills are crucial for achieving high skills. The effectiveness of using all other types of knowledge, which can remain dead weight or actively participate in the service of all types of scientific and pedagogical work, depends on them. The psychological mechanism of realizing these abilities is mental modeling of educational and scientific processes.

Constructive and projective abilities provide a strategic direction of activity and are manifested in the ability to focus on the final goals, solve current problems taking into account the future specialization of students, plan their course and academic activities, determine the importance of the course in the educational process, science, taking into account the necessary connections with other disciplines. This type of capability ensures the implementation of tactical objectives. Designing the course, choosing the content and choosing the forms of conducting classes. Every practitioner must solve the problems of the pedagogical process in the university every day, and every teacher-scientist must study them. Projective abilities are manifested in a special sensitivity to the construction of a pedagogical and scientific "labyrinth" - a path from ignorance to knowledge, they represent the result of future activities and include dosing in the transfer of knowledge, skills, abilities.

Determines sensitivity to the consistent construction of classes and scientific activities in constructive time and space, as a result of which the result corresponds to the plan, the ability to distinguish what needs to be solved now and what needs to be postponed. The creative-constructive component allows you to think, generalize based on insufficient features, and create new combinations using existing information. The basis of projective and constructive activity is intellectual work ability:

- abandon unusual standards and solutions, look for new, original ones;
- look beyond the immediate and obvious;
- covering the essence of the main relations specific to the problem;
- clearly see several different solutions and mentally choose the most effective one;
- the instinct of the existence of a problem where everything seems to have already been solved;
- ideological productivity, etc.

Analyzing this component of abilities, local scientists emphasize the high role of intuition in scientific creativity as a result of a lot of mental work, which allows to shorten the path of knowledge based on quick, almost instantaneous, logical unconscious understanding of knowledge. situation and finding the right solution. In scientific creativity, intuition helps to generate hypotheses. The ability to see the problem, its background, connect with other problems, form hypotheses, find criteria for measuring the studied phenomena, describe, combine and synthesize scientific facts, find their place in the theory.

Research shows that[4], All projective-constructive abilities of teachers without academic degrees, as well as foresight in teaching and scientific work, have decreased. The highest level of these abilities is noted among doctors of science, which is manifested, in particular, in the prevention of conflict situations.

3. Organizational component. Organizational skills serve not only to organize the educational process at the university, but also to self-organize the activity of the teacher. The organizational activity of a modern scientist includes his interaction not only with the object of research, but also with other scientists who participate in research with him or study related

disciplines. General organizational skills L.I.Umansky[5] had learned. He identified 18 typical organizational personality traits:

1. the ability to "charge" other people with your energy;
2. the ability to find the best use for each person;
3. psychological selectivity, the ability to understand the psychology of people and give the right answer;
4. ability to see flaws in other people's actions - criticality;
5. psychological tact - the ability to establish a measure of influence;
6. the general level of development as an indicator of intelligence, the difference in general emotional abilities of a person;
7. genitive - creative and executive;
8. demandingness towards other people;
9. tendency to organizational activity;
10. practicality - the ability to directly, quickly and flexibly apply your knowledge and experience in solving practical problems;
11. independence as opposed to suggestion and blind imitation;
12. observation;
13. self-control, endurance;
14. politeness;
15. perseverance;
16. activity;
17. performance;
18. organization.

Organizational skills are manifested in the ability to organize oneself, time, individual, group and collective activities of students, to gather reliable assistants and like-minded people around a scientific problem.

Research shows that,[4] doctors of science are better than others in organizing the study of research objects, publication of the obtained results, individual scientific work of students, their time and their own learning. Candidates of sciences have the ability to organize collective scientific-research work of students, establish mutual control, criticize and evaluate research results, develop mutual exchange of scientific information and experience in science.

Teachers who do not have a scientific degree are able to organize the study and observation of objects, strive for mutual exchange of scientific information and are ready to participate in complex research.

4. Communication component. Communication in the activity of a teacher is not only a means of scientific-pedagogical communication, but also a condition for improving professional skills and a source of teacher personality development, as well as a means of educating students. Communication skills include:

- the ability to comprehensively and objectively perceive the human communication partner;
- the ability to arouse trust and sympathy in joint activities;
- the ability to anticipate and resolve conflicts;
- fair, constructive and polite criticism of your partner in joint activities;
- perceive and consider criticism, and restructure your behavior and activities accordingly.

The main means of communication are oral and written speech. In scientific activity, unlike pedagogical activity, it plays a primary role in relation to oral communication. Objectification of the results of scientific knowledge, as a rule, is carried out primarily in written speech - in the

process of scientific communication. Oral presentation of research results to a competent audience is a necessary means of verifying the value, objectivity and evidence of research results.

It is interesting to note that the communicative component of abilities - the most flexible, communicative skills - moves towards regression with age.

5. Perceptual-reflexive component. This component of abilities is closely related to the communicative component, which is focused on the subject of pedagogical influence. Reflection means knowing how the acting person perceives it from the communication partner, knowing how the latter understands the reflector. Reflection is a unique double process of the process of reflection of individuals to each other, in which the reflecting subject reflects the inner world of the interlocutor and himself.

Perceptive-reflexive abilities include three types of sensitivity.

1. Sensing the object. This expresses the special sensitivity of the teacher to the attitude of the students to the objects of reality, in this case, to the extent to which the interests and needs of the students are manifested, on the one hand, to the requirements of the pedagogical system. What the teacher himself offers them in the learning process. This sensitivity is similar to empathy and is manifested in quick, easy and deep penetration into the psychology of students, in the emotional identification of the teacher with the student and in their active, purposeful joint activity.

2. A sense of propriety and courtesy. The changes that occur in the student's personality and activities under the influence of various pedagogical tools are manifested with special sensitivity to what changes will occur, whether they are positive or negative, and with what signs they will be evaluated.

3. A sense of belonging to me. It is characterized by the teacher's sensitivity to shortcomings in his work, his criticality and responsibility for the pedagogical and scientific process.

These are the main components of a teacher's professional skills. All of them are closely related to each other and form a single whole that affects the creative individuality and style of a teacher of higher education.

In this article, we tried to determine what components the set of professional skills of a university teacher includes. To do this, we defined abilities as a set of personal qualities that are determined individually, the development of which is influenced by innate (tendency) and social (direction, inclination) factors. Abilities are formed gradually, develop in activity, have a general and special character.

Since abilities are a reflection of activity, we have shown that the professional activity of a university specialist is multifaceted and has several aspects - pedagogical, scientific, methodological, which correspond to a set of components of abilities - epistemological, constructive-projective, organizational, communicative and perceptive, reflective. Having this set of skills helps a teacher of higher education to achieve high skills and an effective influence on the formation of the student's personality, his abilities, which gives him the opportunity for self-awareness in our complex, contradictory world.

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